

An Appraisal of the Principles of Marine Insurance

Bemini Nimibofa Paul^{1*}

¹ Lecturer, faculty of Law, Poma University, Ifangni, Republic of Benin

Accepted Jan 10,2021

Published Feb 04,2021

*Corresponding Author: NIL

DOI

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4511316>

Pages: 226-258

Funding: N/A.

Distributed under
Creative Commons CC BY 4.0

Copyright: © The Author(s)

How to cite this article (APA): N.P. BEMINI (2021) An Appraisal of the Principles of Marine Insurance. *North American Academic Research*, 4(1), 167-180. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4511316>

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

It is generally acknowledged that global commerce depends largely on carriage by sea because of its cost-effectiveness. However, the risks involved are posing very serious challenges. In this context, risk reduction or risk transfer mechanism is an imperative, hence marine insurance. Therefore, the aim of this paper is to appraise the principles guiding marine insurance and their relevance in contemporary times in view of present day commerce in relation to technological advancement.

This study uses both primary and secondary sources. The primary sources are statutes and decided cases. The secondary sources are books, journals and internet sources. All materials used are subjected to context analysis.

The study observed that the extant law have been comparatively effective despite the fact that marine insurance has a great deal of international flavour. However, the study has also observed that some of the provisions in some of the principles shaping marine insurance are weighing more on the policy holders than the underwriters in the balance of justice. The study further identified some of the principles of marine insurance obsolete vis-à-vis modern information technology and are already rendered like toothless bull dogs in the extant law either by virtue of legislative intervention or judicial activism or both.

Therefore, the study concludes that the extant law should be amended to accommodate the realities of modern day commercial activities as well remove or further moderate any provision that will enhance imbalance in relation to justice, since law is the basis of justice.

Keywords: INSURED/ ASSURED/ POLICY HOLDER, INSURER/UNDERWRITER, INSURANCE POLICY, PREMIUM,

Introduction

Marine insurance is acknowledged to be the world's foremost type of insurance. Its history can be traced to the origin of international trade. perhaps, Genova in 1347 was said to be the oldest marine policy and *Ordo super assecuratoribus* (Dubrovnik) was probably one of the oldest insurance legislation which came up around 1562. Although, traces of marine insurance were said to have existed as far back as the 3rd century. Modern principles of marine insurance evolved from the ancient body of maritime laws, which developed from various marine codes. With the

increasing volume of commerce and transport in which, over 80% of the world's importation of goods is done by sea, inherently much risk is increasingly involved as it is estimated that the total annual monetary cost of piracy to the international community is between USD 4.9 and 8.3 billion. Ransoms of about USD 75 – 85 million were paid in 2010 to secure the release of 21 ships. The average ransom payment was about US \$ 4 million. The average length of time that ships are held captive was 214 days¹. And with the faster pace of technological growth in trade and commerce, marine insurance is becoming more relevant than ever before. Therefore it is essential to appraise the principle guiding modern marine insurance. In appraising the principles of marine insurance, it is essential to understand the concept of Insurance generally and how it works, because the same structure is evident in all types of insurance of which marine insurance is one. Then what is insurance?

1.1 Definition of Insurance.

There is no single, generally acceptable definition of Insurance, because it can be defined from the view point of several disciplines including law, economics, history, risk theory, and sociology.² However an examination of a few working definitions of insurance are essential thus: Prof. Dr. Marko Pavliha³ quoting (F. Marks & A. Balla). In his lecture delivered thus:

Contract of insurance is a contract under which one person (the insurer) is legally bound to pay a sum of money or its equivalent to another person (the insured), upon the happening of a specified event involving some element of uncertainty as to time or likelihood of occurrence, which affects the insured's interest in the subject-matter of the insurance (F. Marks & A. Balla). The insured is actually buying his "peace of mind", the "invisible product"

The expression he added, that the insured is buying his "peace of mind", "the invisible product" is worthy of note because it seems to me that, the buying of the peace of mind is the motivation upon which the insured pay the premium agreed in the policy. Furthermore, The Commission on Insurance Terminology of the American Risk and Insurance Association defined Insurance as

"Insurance is the pooling of fortuitous loses by transfer of such risk to insurers, who agree to indemnify insured for such losses, to provide other

¹Prof. Dr. Marko Pavliha, *Overview of Marine Insurance Law*, A lecture delivered on the 7th-10th, January, 2013 at his LL.M class.<available> at <http://www.dpps-mlas.si/wp-content/uploads/2012/12/Overview-of-Marine-Insurance-Law-Prof.-dr.-Marko-600p.m> 23/01/2017

² George E. Rejda, *principles of risk management and Insurance* 11th edition, Pearson Education 2011 pg. 20

³ Lecturer, International Maritime Organization (I.M.O), International Maritime Law Institute, Malta.

pecuniary benefits on their occurrence, or render services connected with the risk⁴”.

The Insurance Mechanism that is, the Insurance risk reduction mechanism is based on the pooling of losses concept as enshrined in the above definition of insurance. Pooling of losses in the heart of insurance.

1.1.1 Pooling of Losses.

According to George E. Rejda,⁵pooling of losses is the spreading of losses incurred by the few over the entire group, so that in the process, average loss is substituted for actual loss. In addition, pooling involves the grouping of a large number of exposure units so that the law of large numbers can operate to provide a substantially accurate prediction of future loss. It is essential to note that pooling is only made easy and profitable by the operation of the law of large numbers. The primary purpose of pooling of losses is to reduce the variation in possible outcomes as measured by the standard deviation⁶ which reduces risk.

1.1.2 The Law of large Numbers – states that the greater the number of exposures, the more closely will the actual results approach the probable results that are expected from an infinite number of exposure.⁷ Having understood the Insurance mechanism, we need to understand what marine Insurance is.

The term marine Insurance is some-how misleading because the contract of marine Insurance can by agreement of parties or custom of the trade, be extended so as to protect the assured against losses in inland waters or land which are incidental to sea voyage.⁸ Under the transit clause an extended marine insurance agreement are frequently made in order to cover the sea voyage as well as the transportation of goods from the warehouse of the seller to that of the overseas buyers. Nevertheless the examination of some definitions of Marine Insurance is very essential.

1.2 Definition of Marine Insurance.

S. 3 of the Marine Insurance Act Cap. M2 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria, 2004 (hereafter called the Act) defined Marine Insurance thus. “A contract of marine insurance is an agreement whereby the insurer undertakes to indemnify the assured in the manner and to the extent thereby agreed,

⁴ Bullentin of the commission on Insurance Technology of the American Risk management and Insurance 11th edition pg. 21

⁵ Author of Principles of Risk management and Insurance 11th edition pg. 21.

⁶ For a better understanding of standard deviation mathematical representation, Engineering mathematics by stroud page 1159 1160.

⁷ Robert 1 melir and Sandra G. Gustavson, Life Insurances theory and Practices, 4th edition (Plano, Tx. Business Publications, 1987) Pg. 31.

⁸ A.G. Buabeng, Marine Insurance claims: Understanding the concepts and Tackling the issues in Maritrade: Papers presented at the International Trade and Maritime Conference 2006 published by Ghana Slippers Council, 2006 pg 33. Mr. A.G. Buabeng, a consultant, maritime legislation IMO

against marine losses that is to say, the losses incidental to marine adventure⁹”.

For the avoidance of ambiguity, The Act further defines marine adventure as any adventure where any ship, goods or other moveable are exposed to maritime perils, such property being referred to in this Act as insurable property; the earning or acquisition of any freight, passage money, commission, profit, or other pecuniary benefit, or the security for any advances, loan, or disbursements, is endangered by the exposure of insurable property to maritime perils; any liability to a third party may be incurred by the owner of, or other person interested in or responsible for, insurable property, by reason of maritime perils¹⁰.

The Act further defined maritime perils thus

For the purposes of this section, "maritime perils" means the perils consequent on, or incidental to, the navigation of the sea, that is to say, perils of the seas, fire, war, perils, pirates, rovers, thieves, captures, seizures, restraints, and detentions of princes and peoples, jettisons, barratry, and any other perils, either of the like kind or which may be designated by the policy¹¹.

According to Prof. J. O. Irukwu, the expression marine Insurance refers to that branch of insurance concerned with the insurance of ships as well as their freight and cargo against maritime risks.¹²It seems the Act was drafted by “Journalists known for paraphrasing the truth in long winded sentences...”¹³ The Learned Professor’s definition has incorporated the long sentences of the Act in a simple sentence and has solved Students’ problem of struggling with long sentences definition.

However, A.G. Buabeng¹⁴, has shown some worry in the business of defining marine insurance, as he noted,

The term “marine insurance” is somewhat misleading because the contract of marine insurance can, by agreement of the parties or custom of the trade, be extended so as to protect the assured against losses on inland waters or land which are incidental to the sea voyage. In export trade, for example, extended marine insurance agreements

⁹ S.3

¹⁰ S.5(2)

¹¹ S.5(3)

¹²Prof. J.O. Irukwu, Marine Insurance, a paper presented at the Maritime seminar for Judges 6th-8th

¹³ Nnaemeka Agu, Justice of the Supreme court of Nigeria, when he defined jurisprudence and completed that statement by saying “... It is therefore my opinion that jurisprudence is philosophy”.

¹⁴ He is a Consultant, Maritime Legislation, International Maritime Organization, Malta.

are made frequently in order to cover not only the sea but also the transportation of goods from the warehouse of the seller to that of the overseas buyer under the transit clause¹⁵.

Ateiza, S.A.¹⁶ in his characteristic erudition, defined marine insurance as follows:

“Marine insurance is that branch of insurance that deals with the coverage of losses or damages that might befall sea and ocean going vessels, the cargo loaded on board and also the related infrastructure in transport by sea”. Although, this definition may not be accepted by all, nevertheless it should be appreciated for being concise, and correctly adding the related infrastructure in the definition.

1.3 The purpose of Marine Insurance.

The purpose of marine Insurance is the provision of relief from financial consequences of the element of risk and uncertainty connected in maritime trade. This relief is actually “the buying of the peace of mind”, the invisible product.

1.4 The functions of Marine Insurance / Economic benefit of marine insurance spread of Risk:

1. Indemnity: If a loss occurs, the insurer will be put back into the same financial position as just prior to the loss. The insured must not profit from the loss.

2. Aid to security: Removes uncertainty of a potential financial loss; individuals and business are more free to expand without need to set aside reserves for future losses.

3. Aid to credit: Loans are not advanced unless item financed is insured, insurance protects creditors’ investments.

4. Sources of employment

5. Loss prevention: The industry contributes to the prevention of losses (mostly through research, education and improved regulations.

1.5 Types of Marine Insurance

Hull insurance (insurance of the vessel with its gear), Cargo insurance (insurance of goods carried by sea), Insurance against the liability of the carrier: protection and indemnity (P & I Clubs), insurance of freight, salvage expenses and general average contributions; insurance of containers, shipyards, etc. are all types of marine insurance.

1.0 DEFINITION OF RELATED TERMS

For an in-depth understanding of the key principles of marine insurance, there is the need to take

¹⁵ A.G. Buabeng, Marine Insurance Claims: Understanding the Concept and Tackling the Issues: a paper presented at the International Trade and Maritime Law Conference, 2006. Organized by Ghana Shippers’ Council, published in *Maritrade*-a publication of the Ghana Shippers’ Council, pg33-94 at 33.

¹⁶ Maritime Law lecturer, University of Abuja. He presented this definition to his students at the LL.B maritime Law class.

an overview of certain insurance concepts.

2.1 Insured / Assured/ Policy holder: He is the party to an insurance cover who is entitled to compensation in monetary terms or by other corresponding terms on the happening of an event insured against.¹⁷

2.2 Insurer/Underwriter: He is the custodian of the fund accumulated with the contributions of the insured. He promises to pay compensation upon the occurrence of the specified event. The insurer is the trustee of the fund and he is therefore expected to.

i. Administer the fund in accordance with the rules and regulations laid down in respect of the fund.

ii. Apply the fund for the purpose for which the funds have been accumulated i.e. payment of claims to insured.

iii. Ensure that the contribution of every individual is commensurate with the risk introduced into the scheme.¹⁸

2.3 Insurance Policy: A contract of marine insurance can only be admitted in evidence if it is embodied in a policy in accordance with the Act.¹⁹ The act further stated the content of the marine insurance policy thus:

A marine policy must contain at least the following particulars:

1. The name of the assured, or some other person who effected the insurance on his behalf.
2. The subject matter insured and the risk insured against;
3. The voyage, the period of time, or both, as the case may be covered by the insurance,
4. The sum or sums insured;
5. The name or names of the insurers.

The policy should be signed by the insurer where the policy is issued on behalf of more than one insurer; each is bound by a separate contract with the assured²⁰.

2.4. Premium is the consideration paid for a contract of insurance²¹

3.0. PRINCIPLES OF MARINE INSURANCE.

It is carefully observed that in the community of scholarship, there are different positions about the same issue. This also has come to play in the academic exercise with reference to the principles of marine insurance. Some writers have only discussed two, others three, and so on. Therefore it is essential to know the meaning of the word "principles". The free online Black's law

¹⁷Kunle Owoseje, An Overview of Marine Cargo insurance practice in Nigeria; in Shipper protection in a Developing economy – insights and strategies. Network publishing 2003 pg 67

¹⁸Ibid

¹⁹S. 24.

²⁰S. 26

²¹<https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/premium>

dictionary²² defined principles as: “[Fundamental](#) truths or doctrines of law; comprehensive rules or doctrines which furnish a basis or origin for others; settled rules of action, procedure, or legal [determination](#)”. Objectively the import of this definition with reference to the issue at stake is that principles of marine insurance are doctrines that furnish a basis for marine insurance. Striking a balance, this study offers a classification, hence insurable interest, utmost good faith and indemnity will be discussed as principles of marine insurance contract and also discuss proximate cause, subrogation and abandonment as principles of marine insurance claim. They are considered below.

3.1.0 Insurable Interest

A person with the legal right to insure a property, must be in a legally recognized relationship to what is insured such that he/she will suffer in a pecuniary sense (financial loss) by the happening of the event insured.

The Act has described insurable as thus:

Subject to the provisions of this Act every person has an insurable interest who is interested in a marine adventure. In particular a person is interested in a marine adventure where he stands in any legal or equitable relation to the adventure or to any insurable property at risk therein, in consequence of which he may benefit by the safety or due arrival of insurable property, or may be prejudiced by its loss, or damage thereto, or by the detention thereof, or may incur liability in respect thereof²³.

3.1.1 Definition of insurable Interests

*Lawrence, J. in Lucena V. Craufurd*²⁴ described insurable interest thus:

A man is interested in a thing to whom advantage may arise or prejudice happen from the circumstances which may attend it...and whom it importeth that its condition as to safety or other quality should continue: Interest does not necessarily imply a right to the whole or a part of a thing, nor necessarily and exclusively that which may be the subject of privation, but the having of some relation, or concern in the subject of the insurance, which relation or concern by the happening of the perils insured against may be so affected as to produce a damage, detriment, or prejudice to the person insuring, and where a man is so circumstanced with respect to matters exposed to certain risks or

²² <http://thelawdictionary.org/principles/> 11:09pm 23/01/2017

²³ S.7.

²⁴ (1806), 2 BOS P.N.R. 269 H.L. (Marine Insurance) p. 302

damages, or to have moral certainty of advantage or benefit, but for those risks and dangers, he may be said to be interested in the safety of the thing. To be interested in the preservation of a thing, is to be so circumstanced with respect to it as to have benefits its existence, prejudice from its destruction.

The property of a thing and the interest devisable from it may be very different; of the first the price is generally the measure, but the interest in a thing, every benefit or advantage arising out of or depending on such thing may be considered as being comprehended.

As earlier mentioned, the purpose of marine insurance is the provision of relief from financial consequence or reimburse the insured for loss resulting from an insured risk. For insured to suffer a loss, it means that he must have an insurable interest²⁵, in the property covered by the marine insurance policy otherwise there is nothing to reimburse as no loss can be said to be suffered.

3.1.2. Peculiarity of Insurable Interest In Marine Insurance.

As a peculiar flavor in insurable interest under marine insurance, the proposer may not or need not have an insurable interest as at the time the marine insurance policy was effected but he must have insurable interest as at the time when the loss occurs²⁶. Generally, insurable interest is usually tied to the passing of the risk, however, it should be noted that under marine insurance policy, risk is usually not passed from the seller to the buyer until and unless all cargo has been loaded on board the ship²⁷

3.1.3.0. Instances of Insurable Interest

The clearest example of an insurable interest under marine insurance is the ownership of cargo on board a ship or the vessel itself²⁸ including part interest, interest in an unfinished vessel and mortgage interest. However, the ship-owner also has an insurable interest in Freight²⁹. Nevertheless, it is noteworthy that if a shipping company owns the vessel, it is the corporation and not the shareholders that are the owners, since a corporation is a legal entity separate from

²⁵ *Balik Furniture and Appliances Ltd v. Maritime Insurance Co. (1978) O.J. No. 1514 (QL); Merchants Marine Insurance Co. of Canada v. Rumsey (1884), 9 S.C.R. 577; Phoenix Assurance v. Golden Imports (1989), 43 C.C.L.I. 313 (B.C. Co. Ct).*

²⁶ *Catherwood Towing v. Commercial Union Assurance (1996), 26 B.C. LR (3d) 57 (C.A)*

²⁷ *Orchard v. Aetna Insurance Co. (1856) 5 U.C.C.P 445 (C.A); Green Forest Lumber v. General Security Insurance, (1980) 1 s.C.r. 176.*

²⁸ *Anchor Marine Insurance v. Keith (1884) 9 S.C.R 483 Clark v. Scottish Imperial Insurance (1897), 4 S.C.R. 192; Crawford v. St. Lawrence Insurance Co (1851) 8 U.C.QB 135 (C.A) Merchants Marine Insurance Co. (1888), 15 S.C.R. 185*

²⁹ *Driscoll v. Millville Marine Insurance Co. (1883), 23 N.B.R. 160 (C.A)*

the shareholders,³⁰ therefore the shareholders or the owners of all the shares of the company do not have an insurable interest.

3.1.3.1. Contingent or Defeasible Interest:

By the operation of the Act, it is not necessary that the insurable interest exist at the time when the policy was effected but it should exist at the time of the loss³¹. Therefore, it follows that a defeasible (voidable) interest is insurable as well as a Contingent (possible but not certain) interest³². For instance, liability for carriage of passengers³³ is insurable and also liability for salvage expense as in the case of *Briggs v. merchants traders' ship and insurance Association*³⁴. Also liability for loss caused by jettison, in case if such Jettison becomes necessary, is insurable.³⁵

According to Dr. Avtar Singh,³⁶

An instance of a defeasible interest is to be found in a case in which certain goods were shipped to a buyer who insured them but subsequently rejected same while still on board and the seller resold them to another buyer. The goods were lost, the original buyer was allowed to sue on the policy, the goods if on arrival, are found to be of merchantable quality. And as such, the buyers' interest in the good is reverted to the seller therefore the buyers' interest in the goods is contingent. The court said that if the plaintiff had an insurable interest at the time that the policy was effected, whatever change may have taken place in the property in the boats since, can have no effect in the relieving the underwriters from their liability as the plaintiff may sue on the policy for the benefit of the party to whom such benefit has passed. Also under the law of sale of goods, a buyer can exercise his right of election to reject

3.1.3.2. Partial Interest

The Act provides that "A partial interest of any nature shall be insurable³⁷". A person having interest in a ship³⁸, in its cargo³⁹ or in its Freight has a right to insure his interest. In the case of *Griffiths v. Branley*⁴⁰; it was held that the subject matter of insurance was the one-third loss of freight as a result of sea-damage and that the plaintiffs were entitle to recover from the insurance company such proportion of the amount of the loss.

³⁰ *Salomon v. A Salomon & Co., (1897) A.C. 22* Under the United States of America law, this is not the same as shareholders are permitted to have an insurable interest. See A.L. Parks. The Law and Practice of Marine Insurance and Average 2nd edition (centreville, M.D. Cornell Maritime Press, 1987) at page 524.

³¹ S.8

³² S. 9(1) of the Marine Insurance Act cap 216 LFN 1990 provides this "A defeasible interest shall be insurable as also shall be contingents interest.

³³ *Gibson v. Bradford, (1855) 4 E & B 586: 119ER 215*

³⁴ *(1849) 13 QB 167:116 ER 1227*

³⁵ *Stephen v. Australian Insurance Co. (1872) LR 8 CP 18:43 LJ CP 12*

³⁶ Avtar Singh Law of Insurance 2nd Edition 2010 Eastern Book Company Luck now.at page 255

³⁷ S. 10

³⁸ *Robertson v. Hamilton, (1811) 14 East 522: 104ER 708*

³⁹ *Peise v. Aguitar (1811) 3 Taunt 506: 128 ER 201*

⁴⁰ *(1878) 4 QBD 70 (CA)*

3.1.3.3. Reinsurance

An insurer may take a reinsurance for the purpose of managing the risk he has undertaken if he feels and for his own protection. The insurer under such situation has an insurable interest in his risk. This practice is provided for in the Act as thus “The insurer under a contract of marine insurance has an insurable interest in his risk, and may reinsure in respect of it but unless the policy otherwise provides, the original Assured shall have no right or interest in respect such reinsurance”⁴¹.

3.1.3.4. Bottomry and Respondentia

The Act also provides that “The lender of money on bottomry or respondentia has an insurable interest in respect of the loan”⁴². Therefore he can effect a policy on the ship to the extent of his interest.

3.1.3.5. Masters and Seamen’s wages

The Act as provides that: “The Master of any member of the crew of a ship has an insurable interest in respect of his wages”⁴³.

3.1.3.6. **Advance Freight:** The Act provides that “In the case of advance freight, the person advancing the freight has an insurable interest in so far as such freight is not repayable in case of loss”⁴⁴. This provision implies that the freight paid by consignor must be at risk (i.e. the freight is not refundable to him in the event of any loss of goods.

In *Mansfield v Maitland*⁴⁵, where freight paid in advance was paid in the form of a loan to the carrier, the court held that the consignor had no insurable interest in that kind of advance freight payment. Since it is a loan by the freighter, he can only have a remedy against the owner for the debt⁴⁶.

3.1.3.7. **Charges of Insurance:** The Act provides thus: “The assured has an insurable interest in the charges of any insurance which he may effects”⁴⁷

3.1.3.8 The Act also provides for **Quantum of insurable interest** as thus:

Where the subject matter insured is mortgaged, the mortgagor has an insurable interest in the full value thereof, and the mortgagee has an insurable interest in respect of any sum due or to become due under the mortgage. A mortgagee, consignee or other person having an

⁴¹ S.11

⁴² S.12

⁴³ S.13

⁴⁴ S.14

⁴⁵ (1821) 4 B & Ald 582: 106 ER 1049

⁴⁶ *Hicks v. Shield* (1857) 7 E & B 633: 119 ER 1380

⁴⁷ S. 15

interest in the subject matter insured may insure on behalf and for the benefit of other persons interested as well as for his own benefit. The owner of insurable property has an insurable interest of the full value thereof, notwithstanding that some third person may have agreed or be liable, to indemnify him in case of loss⁴⁸.

3.2.0 THE PRINCIPLE OF UTMOST GOOD FAITH

3.2.1 Introduction

The contract of marine insurance is a contract of utmost Good faith like every other contract of insurance.

The Act provided that: "A contract of marine insurance is a contract based upon the utmost good faith, and if the utmost good faith is not observed by either party, the contract may be avoided by the other party⁴⁹

From this provision, it should be noted that:

The utmost good faith is to be observed by both parties to a contract of insurance, and thus imposes a duty of disclosure on both parties. In respect to the proposed risk this obligation is aimed at bringing both parties to a state of equal knowledge from the time negotiations are commenced. This is in consonance with the trite principle of contract law that parties must be of the same mind for a contract to be enforced.

3.2.2. An imbalance in the Application Utmost good faith

Although the duty arising from this principle of Utmost good faith is imposed on both parties to a marine insurance contract, generally in practice the burden tends to fall often on the insured than the insurer. This practice is being strengthened by the Act as it provides thus:

Subject to the provision of this section, the assured shall disclose to the insurer, before the contract is concluded, every material circumstance which is known to the assured, and the assured shall be deemed to know every circumstance which, in the ordinary course of business, ought to know by him. If the assured fails to make such disclosure, the insurer may avoid the contract. Every circumstance is material which would influence the judgment of a prudent insurer in fixing the Premium, in determining whether he will take the risk⁵⁰.

3.2.3. The possibility of degrees of Good Faith?

The use of the word "Utmost" seems to imply the possibilities of different degrees of Good Faith

⁴⁸ S.16

⁴⁹ S. 19

⁵⁰ S. 20 (1) – (2)

but this possibility is in much doubt as Lord Stephenson in *CTI v. Oceanus Mutual Underwriting Association (Bermuda)*⁵¹ with such reservation said “it is enough that much more than an absence of bad faith is required of both parties to all contracts of insurance”. From the foregoing, it can safely be said that “the word “Utmost” is intended to suggest a high degree of good faith. In other words, in discharging the duty of full disclosure, the proposer must ensure that what is proposed to the insurer is true and correct⁵² otherwise the insurer has the option to avoid the contract of insurance⁵³.

3.2.4. Materiality of Circumstances

Every circumstance is said to be material which will influence the judgment of a prudent insurer in fixing a premium or in determining whether he will take the risk⁵⁴. If a marine policy was taken after the ship had sailed, the insured has a duty to disclose the date the vessel started sailing at the time the policy was taken⁵⁵. It should be noted that the duty to prove materiality of any undisclosed information lies with the insurer⁵⁶.

3.2.5. Polishing the Duty of Disclosure

Narrowing the flood gate of Disclosure litigations by the United Kingdom Courts, as a result of the frequent litigations on disclosure problems, the courts (especially in the U.K) in recent years have polished the duty of disclosure arising from this important marine insurance principle of Utmost good faith, by introducing the notion of “decisive influence” and “inducement” during the contractual negotiations⁵⁷. In the case of *Manifest shipping & Co v. Uni-Polaris Insurance Co. (The STarsea)*⁵⁸, it was held that although the duty of utmost good faith continued to apply after the contract was originally concluded, this was not the same as the duty owed at the pre-contractual stage. Therefore only fraud in the claims process would defeat a claim while the only duty imposed on the assured was to act honestly⁵⁹. Furthermore, it was held that an insurer may not avoid the contract unless it can be shown that a fraud was relevant to the insurer’s ultimate liability under the policy to the extent that it would entitle the termination of the policy⁶⁰.

⁵¹ 1984 Lloyd’s Rep 476 at p. 525

⁵² *Strive shipping Corp. v. Hellemie Mutual War Risk Association (The Grecia Expression)* [2002] 2 Lloyd’s L.R. 88

⁵³ *Inter Municipality Realty & Development Corp. v. Gore Mutual Insurance Co.*, (978) 2 F.C. 691, *Degreeot v. J.T. O’Byran and Co.* (1979), 15 BCLR 271 (C.A)

⁵⁴ *Descrosiers v. Fishing Vessel Insurance Plan* (1994), 87 F.T.R 101

⁵⁵ *Peterson Agencies Nigeria Ltd. V. Merary Agencies Company Ltd* (1994 F.H.CLR 25

⁵⁶ *Amo containers v. Drake Insurance* (1984) 51 Nfld & P.E.I.R. 55 (Nfld. S.C. (T.D)), *1013799 Ontario Ltd v. Kent Line International* (2000). 22 C.C.L.I. (3d) 312 (Omt. S.C)

⁵⁷ *Container Transport International Inc. v. Oceanus – underwriters Association (Bermuda) Ltd.* (1984) 1 Lloyd’s L.R 476; *Pan Atlantic Insurance Co. v. Pine Top Insurance Co.* (1995) AC 501

⁵⁸ (2001) 1 Lloyd’s L.R. 389 (HL)

⁵⁹ *ibid*

⁶⁰ *Agapitos v. Agnew (The Aegeon)* [200] 2 Lloyd’s L.R. 42 See *Edgar Gold, ALDO Chircop, Hugh kindred of Canadian Law – Maritime Law pg 32*

3.2.6.0 . Modern application of the Duty of Disclosure and Utmost good faith principle

There seems to appear some considerable shift from the common law application of the duty of disclosure arising from the fundamental insurance principle of utmost good faith. In some jurisdiction, this shift is effected through judicial intervention and while for some, it is effected by way of legislative changes.

3.2.6.1. Overseas Perspective

Particularly, in the London market, questions are being raised for instance in respect to the duty of disclosure and the adherence of the utmost good faith in its original common law form, on the following grounds.

One, that in the 21st century, the situation as regards obtaining, collating and transmitting information is totally different from what obtained in the 18th century. Two, that the interest of some insured may actually be disadvantaged if the same strict firm and stiff application of the principle were allowed to continue. An example is cited in the recent English case of the North Star⁶¹ in a recent lecture on the topic materiality, non-disclosure and false allegations: following the North Star? James Davey an English legal luminary stated as quoted thus:⁶²

The Court of Appeal decision in the North Star show continuing judicial dissatisfaction with the doctrine of utmost good faith in insurance contract law. As a vehicle designed in the 18th century to counteract inequalities of access to information, it has failed to keep pace with modern circumstances. However, the most recent “hard” case represents an age old problem: Whether to require disclosure of information known to the insured to be untrue, but not yet disproven⁶³

The undeveloped nature of the doctrine of utmost good faith in insurance law has once again come under the scrutiny of the Court of Appeal, in the North Star. It appears that reform is closer than it has been for some time. Waller LJ began his review of the relevant legal principles by noting “[t]he law in this area is ..., capable of producing serious injustice” and concluded by welcoming the future review of the

⁶¹ *North Star Shipping Ltd and Ors v. Sphere Drake Insurance (The North Star)* (2006) 691 LMLN2 available at <http://www.simic.net.cn/news - show.php?id 15025 17/01/2017 10.51pm>

⁶² *ibid*

⁶³ The facts relating to the ground upon which the appeal was dismissed was that, “the insurer alleged that they were entitled to avoid the policies for misrepresentation and non disclosure of a number of matters, including the existence of various pending criminal proceedings in the Greek courts against and /MP (Brothers who beneficially owned the shipping company) in which allegations of dishonesty had been made, but in respect of which HP and MP had subsequently been acquitted or it had been decided that charge should not proceed to trial. Moreover, a letter had been written by the serious fraud office which stated that it regarded HP as having been the victim of a fraud by other” parties <https://www.i.law.com/ilaw/doc/view.htm?id = 130514> > accessed 17/01/2017 11:27 pm

area by the Law Commission. This focus on Legislative interference rather than judicial reform, was shared by Longmore LI while noting the interest of the Law Commission, this paper focuses on the scope for judicial intervention, as the Law Commission has previously called for reform of the doctrine of utmost good faith with little success.

Issues to note:

The crucial question is, did the Court of Appeal avert her mind to the trite law of the assumption of innocence operative in criminal law since this was particularly relevant to allegations of serious criminal conduct, such as in the North Star? If yes, it seems to me, that criminal cases which were not proven beyond reasonable doubt should not have form the ground of materiality in the circumstances.

Secondly, it appears to me that the position of the Court of Appeal in the North Star case would have been different if inducement was the ground of appeal. That, the so called material fact does not have a decision influence or inducement at the time of the contractual negotiations.

3.2.6.2. The Nigerian reformation by legislation (INSURANCE ACT 2003)

The Insurance Act, provides that it is applicable to all insurance businesses⁶⁴ under S. 2 (1)⁶⁵, marine insurance is classified under general insurance business. Therefore it is safe to conclude that the Insurance Act, 2003 is a Consolidating Act of general effect and application.⁶⁶

Therefore the provisions of S. 54(1)⁶⁷(under Part IX-Disclosure, condition and warranty) which specifically mention that "... Any information not specifically requested shall be deemed not to be material.

The Insurance Act, 2003 provides.

In a contract of insurance, a breach of term whether called a warranty or a condition shall not give rise to any right by or afford a defense to the insurer unless the term is material and relevant to the risk loss insured against. Notwithstanding any provision in any written law or enactment to the contrary, where there is a breach of term of a contract of insurance, the insurer shall not be entitled to repudiate the whole or any part of the contract a claim brought on the grounds of the breach. Unless the breach amounts to a fraud or it is a breach of fundamental term of contract⁶⁸.

From the foregoing, the Nigerian Insurance Act 2003 has cut down the effect or warranty,

⁶⁴ S. 1

⁶⁵ The Insurance Act, 2003.

⁶⁶ *Jumbo United Co. Ltd v. Leadway Assurance Co. Ltd* (2016) 15 N.W.L.R. 363-532 at 446.

⁶⁷ Insurance Act 2003

⁶⁸ S. 55 (1)-(2)

disclosure and the principle of utmost good faith.

3.2.6.3. The Common Law Position of the Reciprocal duties of Utmost good faith

By the provision of the Act, the duty of utmost good faith is reciprocal⁶⁹. This is adopted from the common Law, as Lord Justice Stade on appeal remark in the case of *Banque Keyser Ullman v. Skandia*⁷⁰, remarked that "obligation to disclose material facts is a mutual one imposing reciprocal duties on the insurer and the insured"

Nevertheless, the common law position has been changed fundamentally in Ghana. Insurance Law 1989, PNDCL 277, as amended, introduced some amendments to the common law of insurance. Under Part IV of the Law captioned "supplementary and Miscellaneous Provisions" some amendment were made S. 57(1) of the Law⁷¹ provides. Thus, a party to a contract of insurance shall not be under an obligation to disclose any fact about which no question is asked by the insurer or his agent".

S. 57(2) of the Law⁷² also provides thus:

Notwithstanding subsection (1) of this section, where a party to a contract of insurance with intent to avoid the rejection of the risk by the insurer or the payment of higher premiums, conceals from or fails to disclose to the other party to the contract any fact which he knows or believes or has reasons to believe to be material to the contract, the contract may be rescinded by that other party.

From the foregoing, S. 57(1) of the law⁷³ is to the effect that the duty of disclosure is not reciprocal. It is also crystal clear that from S. 57(2) of the law⁷⁴ that despite the elegant drafting, that the remedy for non-disclosure is rescission of the contract, not avoidance of the contract which is the common Law position.

Summarily, it can be seen from the above adumbrations that, in the modern times, the insured is less vulnerable as it were in the application of the duty of disclosure arising from the utmost good faith principle has put the insured in a less vulnerable position.

3.3.0 THE MARINE INSURANCE PRINCIPLE OF INDEMNITY

3.3.1. Measure of Indemnity

In the words of the Act, the meaning of measure of indemnity is given thus:

For the purposes of this section "measure of indemnity" means the sum which the assured may recover in respect of a loss on a policy by

⁶⁹ S. 10

⁷⁰ (1987) 1 Lloyd's Rep. 69 at 9. 93

⁷¹ Ghana Insurance Law 1989

⁷² ibid

⁷³ ibid

⁷⁴ ibid

which he is insured, being in the case of a valued policy the full extent of the value fixed by the policy, and in the case of an unvalued policy, the full extent of the insurable value⁷⁵.

The expression “measure of indemnity” means the right of the assured to recover in the case of an unvalued policy, the full extent of the insurance value and, in the case of a valued policy, the full of the value fixed by the policy⁷⁶. A marine insurance contract is legally a contract of indemnity in that the insurer undertakes to indemnify the assured in the manner and to the extent thereby agreed against losses that are incidental to marine adventure⁷⁷. Most a times, the measure of indemnity has been agreed at the conclusion of the insurance contract. However, such an agreed indemnity may be more even less, than the ideal pecuniary indemnity⁷⁸. This peculiarity in marine insurance is due to the fact that some marine insurance policies are classified as valued and some unvalued⁷⁹.

3.3.2.0 Classification of Marine Insurance Policy and the Effect on the Principle of Indemnity

3.3.2.1 Valued Marine Insurance Policy

In valued marine insurance policy, the value of the subject matter is expressly stated and, in the absence of fraud, this value is conclusive and binding on the parties to the contract. Most cargo marine policies as well as most of the hull and machinery policies are valued, so that in the absence of fraud, even those that are vastly overvalued are acceptable and not construct as fraud as held in the case of *General Shipping and forwarding Co. v. British General Insurance Co. (The Borre)*⁸⁰. For instance, Borre was insured for €2,000 under a policy in which the vessel’s value was stated to be €5,000=. In effect this was under-insurance⁸¹ as the assured assumed €3,000 of the ship’s total value (i.e. the difference between the agreed value of the ship and the value covered by the insurer in the policy). In fact, the market value of the ship was €1,500 only. The ship became a total loss and the insurer was compelled to pay €2,000. The insurer protested on the ground that the ship was grossly overvalued. The court held; that the assured’s claim should succeed, as there was

⁷⁵ Section 68(2), Marine Insurance Act Cap M2 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria, 2004.

⁷⁶ Dr. Avtar Singh: Law of Insurance 2010 Easter Book Company Lucknow 2nd Edition 2010 pg 294

⁷⁷ Sec. 3 of the Marine Insurance Act Cap. M2 LFN 2004

⁷⁸ *Goole and Hull Steamship Towing Co. v. Ocean Marine Insurance Co (1929)*, 29LI LR 242

⁷⁹ Marine Insurance Act Cap M2 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria, 2004.

⁸⁰ (1923) 15 LI.L.R. 175

⁸¹ Under-insurance connotes that the subject-matter is insured for a smaller amount than the stated value of that subject-matter in the policy. As it is in the case of *General Shipping and forwarding Co. v. British General Insurance Co.*, The Borre was insured for €2,000 while the stated value in the policy in respect of the ship was €5,000

no evidence of fraud, see also the case of *Fudge v. Charter Marine Insurance*⁸². Therefore under a valued policy, the assured is entitled to recover the sum, fixed by the policy if the subject-matter insured is a total loss.⁸³

On the other hand, if under a valued marine insurance policy, a ship is under insured, and the ship is a partial loss; then the insurer will only pay proportionally in terms of measure of indemnity. For example, had it been, in the case of *The Borre* is a partial loss, requiring repairs costing only €500, then the insurer would only have to pay 4% of €500= which is €200= only, because €2,000=which was the insurance coverage is just 4% of €5,000= which was the stated value of the vessel in the policy. This implies that, the remaining €300= is the responsibility of the Ship owner⁸⁴, who by conduct has positioned himself as the second underwriter (underwriter by conduct) by virtue of under-insuring his vessel. The same condition applies even when there several underwriters insuring one vessel and the vessel is under-insured.

3.3.2.2 Unvalued Marine Insurance Policy

In unvalued marine insurance policy, no specific value is stated and in the event of a loss, payment will be the insurable value which is to be calculated under general insurance principle as set out by the extant law⁸⁵. S. 18 of the extent law provides;

Subject to the express provision or valuation in the policy, the insurable value of the subject matter insured shall be ascertained as follows: In insurance on Ship, the insurable value which in the case of steamship, includes also machinery, boilers, and coals and engine stores if owned by the assured, and, in the case of a ship engaged in a special trade, the ordinary fittings requisite for that trade, is the value, at the commencement of the risk, of the ship, including her outfit, provisions and stores for the officers and crew, money advanced for seamen's wages, and other disturbances (if any) incurred to make the ship fit for the voyage or adventure contemplated by the policy plus the charges of insurance upon the while; In insurance on freight, whether paid in advance or otherwise, the insurable value is the gross amount of the

⁸²(1992), 97 Nfld. & P.E. I.R. 91 (Nfld. S.C)

⁸³ S.69 (a), Marine Insurance Act, 2003

⁸⁴ S. 82 of the Marine Insurance Act provides thus; "Where the assured is insured for an amount less than the insurable value or, in the case of a valued policy, for an amount less than the policy valuation, he shall be deemed to be his own insurer in respect of the uninsured balance".

⁸⁵Marine Insurance Act, 2003

freight at the risk of the assured, plus the charges of insurance; In insurance on goods or merchandise, the insurable value is the prime cost of the property insured, plus the expenses of and incidental to shipping and the charges of insurance upon the whole; In insurance on any other subject-matter, the insurable value is the amount at the risk of the assured when the policy attaches, plus the charges of insurance.

The legal and practical differences between the two types of policies can be easily captured in the following example. Where a ship has an actual value of £200,000 as at the time of loss and the ship is a total loss, under the unvalued policy, covering losses up to £400,000, the owner will recover £200,000, while under a valued policy in which the agreed value of the ship is £400,000, the owner will recover the actual extent of his or her loss as determined by the policy, that is £400,000.

3.3.4 The scheme of proportionality in relation to total or partial loss

Still under a valued marine insurance policy, this system of proportionality does not cover partial losses when the ship is over insured. For an example, if a ship is valued at £5,000= but it is insured for £10,000= and a partial loss occurs resulting to a damage worth £4,000, the assured does not recover the ten-fifth (10/5th) or 200% of the amount of the partial loss, which is £8,000= but only the £4,000=. This is due to the fact that the assured is only entitled to the “reasonable cost of the repairs”. However, where the ship is a total loss, the owner would have his full amount (£5,000).

3.4.0. THE PRINCIPLE OF PROXIMATE CAUSE.

This is the most important principle to observe when it comes to handling insurance claims. In examining the validity of claims, remote causes are never given a chance. It is not just enough to assert that one or more of the perils insured against are in effect, but a claimant must also establish that such perils are the proximate cause of the disaster giving rise to the claim. Therefore, there can be a possibility of a loss occurring without a claim under the policy merely because the cause had not been established to be proximate. It is therefore, worthy of note that, this legal principle has been given statutory backing in marine insurance, although not without a caveat.

The Act provides thus:

Subject to the provisions of this Act and unless the policy otherwise provides, the insurer shall be liable for any loss proximately caused by a peril insured against, but, subject, as aforesaid, he shall not be liable for any loss which is not proximately caused by a peril insured against. In particular-the insurer shall not be liable for any loss attributable to the willful misconduct of the assured, but unless the policy otherwise

provides, he shall be liable for any loss proximately caused by a peril insured against, even though the loss would not have happened but for the misconduct or negligence of the master or crew; unless the policy otherwise provides, the insurer of ship or goods shall not be liable for any loss proximately caused by delay, although the delay be caused by a peril insured against; unless the policy otherwise provides, the insurer shall not be liable for ordinary wear and tear, ordinary leakage and breakage, inherent vice or nature of the subject-matter insured, or for any loss proximately caused by rats or vermin, or for any injury to machinery not proximately caused by maritime perils⁸⁶.

3.4.1 Definition of Proximate Cause

Proximate cause was defined in the case of *Pawsey v Scottish Union & National Insurance Company (1908)* as: "the active and efficient cause that sets in motion a train of events which brings about a result, without the intervention of any force started and working actively from a new and independent source"⁸⁷.

The proximate cause is not necessarily the latest cause, but it must be direct, dominant, effective and efficient cause of the loss.⁸⁸

3.4.2. The purpose of the Principle of Proximate Cause. The purpose of the principle of proximate cause is to ascertain whether the loss was caused by the peril insured against.

3.4.3. Operation of the Principle of Proximate Cause. In *P. Samuel & Co. Ltd v. Damus*⁸⁹ the approximate cause of the loss of the insured vessel was scuttling. The House of Lords held that, the insurers were not liable because the Marine Insurance Act 1906, specifically stated in Section 55(1) that insurers would only be liable for any loss proximately caused by a peril insured against and scuttling was not a peril insured against⁹⁰

3.4.4.0. The Application of the Principle of Proximate Cause. The application of this doctrine will vary according to circumstance whether (I) The last of the successive causes happen to be the peril insured against. (II) The peril insured against is not the last cause but a preceding cause (III) The causes are not successive but concurrent in operation

3.4.4.1. Where the Last Cause is the Peril Insured Against. Where the last of the successive causes happens to be the peril insured against, the lost is said to be caused by the peril insured

⁸⁶ S. 56(1)-(2)

⁸⁷ -<http://www.cila.co.uk/cila/downloads/getting-qualified/certificate/files-2/205-chapter-8-proximate-cause>"

⁸⁸ -J.O. Irukwu, Insurance Law and Practice in Nigeria,(revised Ed The caxton Press(West Africa) Limited Ibadan 1981)pg. 73

⁸⁹ (1924) All E.R. Rep. 66,H.L.,

⁹⁰ .see also *Leyland Shipping Co., Ltd. v. Norwich Union Fire Insurance Society, as reported, [1917] 1 K.B. 873 C.A (marine insurance).*

against⁹¹. Therefore it becomes needless to begin to find out which of the preceding event brought the peril into play. In *Redman v. Wilson*,⁹² where a ship having been injured by negligent loading, and becoming leaky in consequence, was run ashore to prevent her sinking and to save her cargo, and the Court held that there was a loss by peril of the sea, notwithstanding the prior negligence and subsequent voluntary stranding.

3.4.4.2. Where the peril insured against is not the last cause. Where the peril insured against is not the last cause but a preceding cause, it becomes needful to know whether the last cause was so intimately connected with the peril insured against, either immediately or by transmission through a chain of circumstances, and the loss will be counted as been within the policy especially where there is no break in the sequence of causes as in the case of *William France, Fenwick & Co., Ltd v. Merchants' Marine Insurance Ltd.*,⁹³. Where an insured ship came into collision with a second ship, the impact being slight, but the second ship in consequence, collided with a third ship, doing considerable damage, for which the insured ship was held liable, and it was held that the damages payable in respect of the last ship, were damages in consequence of collision. However, the position will reverse where the sequence of causes is interrupted⁹⁴.

3.4.4.3. Where the Causes are concurrent. Where in operation the causes are concurrent, and continue to operate on the subject matter of the insurance until they cause the loss, the loss is attributed to one cause as much as to the other. If therefore, one of the causes is the peril insured against, the cause of the loss is the peril insured against and the existence of the other cause is disregarded⁹⁵

3.5.0 THE PRINCIPLE OF SUBROGATION

5.1 Definition of Subrogation. Subrogation is a term denoting a legal right reserved by most insurance carriers. Subrogation is the right for an insurer to legally pursue a third party that caused an insurance loss to the insured. This is done as a means of recovering the amount of the claim paid by the insurance carrier to the insured for the loss⁹⁶

3.5.2. The Operation of the Doctrine.

The doctrine of subrogation is the right of the Insurer having fulfilled his obligation to step into the shoes of the insured when a loss has been paid. Where the insurer has fully indemnified the insured against damage caused by a third party tortfeasor, the insurer would as of right become entitled to take over the right of the insured's right to seek recovery from the third party tortfeasor.

⁹¹ *Trew v. Railway Passengers' Assurance Co. (1861)*, 6 H. & N. 839, Ex.Ch.;

⁹² (1845), 14 M. & W. 476 (marine insurance).

⁹³ [1915] 3 K.B. 290, C.A. (marine insurance)

⁹⁴ *Pink v. Fleming* (1890), 25 Q.B.D. 396, C.A.

⁹⁵ *Dudgeon v. Prembroke* (1877), 2 App. Cas. 284 (marine insurance)

⁹⁶ <http://www.investopedia.com/terms/s/subrogation.asp>

This principle ensures that the insured shall not make profit out of a loss⁹⁷, likewise the Insurer is not allowed to make profit as enshrined in the case of *Yorkshire Insurance Co. Ltd., v. Nisbet Shipping Co. Ltd.*⁹⁸. In this case, a vessel was insured for £72,000= and it became a total loss in 1945 as a result of the collision with Canadian vessel.

3.5.3 Legal Strength of Subrogation

The Act, in establishing the doctrine of Subrogation and conferring a right upon an insurer who pays for total loss, provides thus;

Where the insurer pays for a total loss, either of the whole, or in the case of goods of any apportionable part, of the subject-matter insured, he shall thereupon become entitled to take over the interest of the assured in whatever may remain of the subject-matter so paid for, and shall thereby be subrogated to all the rights and remedies of the assured in and in respect of that subject-matter as from the time of the casualty causing the loss⁹⁹.

Furthermore, the Act, in showing the legal strength of the doctrine equally confers similar rights upon an insurer who pays for partial loss, hence providing that;

Subject to the foregoing provisions, where the insurer pays for a partial loss, he shall acquire no title to the subject-matter insured, or such part of it as may remain, but shall thereupon be subrogated to all rights and remedies of the assured in and in respect of the subject-matter insured as from the time of the casualty causing the loss, in so far as the assured has been indemnified, according to this Act, by such payment for the loss¹⁰⁰.

3.5.4. Restitutory Purpose of Subrogation

Under an insurance contract (between the insurer and the Insured), it is usually the wrong action of a third party that usually give rise to the loss suffered by the Insured at the first instance. This loss is transferred to the Insurer by the operation of the principle of indemnity. If the insured still retains a right of action against the third party, the two possibilities are either; the Insured would bring an action against the third party (wrong-doer) thereby recovering twice for his loss or the Insured having being indemnified by the Insurer, would refuse to take any legal action against the Third party (wrong-doer) thereby allowing him to escape responsibility for the wrong he perpetrated. These two situations are obviously undesirable. It is for the purposes of avoiding these

⁹⁷ *Castellian v. Preston*(1883), 7 A.C. 333 Q.B.(a case of partial indemnification)

⁹⁸ (1961) 2 All E.R. 487, Q.B.D.

⁹⁹ S. 80(1),

¹⁰⁰ S. 80(2)

undesirable conditions, that this principle of subrogation come to play, such that the third party (wrong-doer) can suffer for his action, by way of restoring the Insurer back to position with neither the Insured nor the Insurer making profit out the loss. Thus subrogation is a restitutionary measure¹⁰¹ and its creation is to prevent the unjust enrichment of either the insured or the Third party (wrong-doer)¹⁰².

3.5.5.0 Significant Legal Issues on Subrogation.

3.5.5.1. The issue of partial indemnification

Even when there is a situation whereby the amount in the policy is less than the value of the subject-matter, the insurer may claim that subrogation entitles him to all of the remedies of the insured, including the right to recover for the full amount of the injuries sustained. In the case of *The Livingstone*¹⁰³ the insurer of a ship which sunk in a collision with the Livingstone paid \$25,000 on a valued policy to the owners. The sunken ship was actually worth \$37,500, and this amount was recovered from the tortfeasor. After the insurance company was paid \$25,000, both the insurer and the owners claimed the remaining \$12,500. It was the insurer's position that it was subrogated to all the rights of the owners, while the owners insisted they were to be indemnified for their uninsured loss.¹⁰⁴

The Second Circuit, in awarding the \$12,500 to the insured, said

. . . that subrogation does not permit one party to secure an unfair advantage over the other; it does not permit the insurer to speculate, or profit or drive an unconscionable bargain. When he is paid in full, equity requires the return of the balance to the insured in payment of his uncompensated loss¹⁰⁵.

. . . [Equity and good conscience do not require the court to go further and permit [the insurer] to realize an enormous profit from the transaction. This remedy clearly satisfies the principle of indemnification. Profit to the insurance company could only have come at the direct expense of the owners¹⁰⁶.

3.5.5.2. The Issue of Full Indemnification

In the second type of case, both the insured and insurer have been indemnified and there is the

¹⁰¹ *Castellain v. Preston*, 11 Q.B.D. 380, 386 (1883):

¹⁰² *American Sur. Co. v. Bethlehem Nat'l Bank*, 33 F. . Supp. 722,723 (E.D. Pa.).

¹⁰³ 130 F. 746 (2d Cir.), cert. denied

¹⁰⁴ Facts ,op cit, pg.148 Jay S. Bybee, Profits in Subrogation : An Insurer's Claim to Be More than Indemnified, 1979 BYU L. Rev. 145 (1979). Available at: <http://digi.talcommons.law.byu.edu/lawreview/vol1979/iss1/3>

¹⁰⁵ Ibid.

¹⁰⁶ Ibid.

possibility of recovering additional funds. In the case of *Yorkshire Insurance Co. v. Nisbet Shipping Co.*¹⁰⁷, a vessel was insured for £72,000= and it became a total loss in 1945 as a result of collision with Canadian vessel. The Insurer paid the Insured and the Insurer exercised his right of subrogation against the Canadian government and succeeded. But meanwhile, the pound sterling devalued in 1949 and the loss when converted into English currency came to around £127,000= both the insurer and the insured contended to retain the balance of £55,000= The court held that the action of the Insurer failed.

Justice Diplock carefully reviewed the major English subrogation decisions as well as the decision in *The Livingstone*¹⁰⁸ and concluded that the insurance company was entitled only to the amount it had paid the insured, £72,000. The Court stated that the rule it adopted "renders irrelevant any consideration of the particular concatenation (inter-connectedness) of circumstances which enable the assured to recover from the Canadian Government a sum in sterling in excess of the value of the ship at the time of the casualty"¹⁰⁹.

3.5.5.3. Issues on Subrogation as a Right

The right of Subrogation is not an automatic one. It cannot and does not arise until and unless the Insurer have admitted the assured's claim¹¹⁰ and have paid¹¹¹ the sum under the policy¹¹². The primary rights in respect of which the Insurer may be entitled to subrogation can arise out :

(I). Of Tort which must be connected with the loss so as to make the tortfeasor¹¹³ responsible for the damages to the assured¹¹⁴, but where the insured becomes the cause of his damage, he will lose the right of subrogation.¹¹⁵

(II) Of Contract, if the contract imposes upon a third the obligation of making compensation to the assured in the event of the loss and the benefit of the obligation clearly passes to the insurer¹¹⁶. For instance, where goods are lost or destroyed in the hand of a Bailee such as carrier, the insurer may sue the Bailee upon the contract of bailment.¹¹⁷

(III) Under Statute, if the assured would be able to recover, under the terms of a statute, the whole or part of his loss, then the insurer can subrogate to his right¹¹⁸

(IV) Over the Subject- matter where, notwithstanding the happening of a total loss, there is a sufficient amount of salvage which possess some value, the assured cannot claim both to receive

¹⁰⁷ [1962] 2 Q.B. 330.

¹⁰⁸ 130 F. 746 (2d Cir.), cert. denied,

¹⁰⁹ [1962] 2 Q.B. at 346.

¹¹⁰ *Midland Insurance Co. v. Smith*(1881),6 Q.B.D 561 per *Watkin Williams J. at p. 564*

¹¹¹ *Page v. Scottish Insurance Corporation* (1929), 140 L.T.571, C.A.

¹¹² *Mason v. Sainbury* (2nd Edn., 1974) pg 481-488

¹¹³ See E.R. Hardy Ivamy, *General principles of Insurance Law* (3rd ed., London butterworth, 1975) pg445.

¹¹⁴ *Assicuraizoni Generali Tristle v. Express Assurance Corporation Ltd.*,[1907]2 K.B. 814 (*Marine Insurance*).

¹¹⁵ *Simpson v. Thompson* (1877), 3 App. Cas. 279 (*Marine insurance*.)

¹¹⁶ *North British and Mercantile Insurance Co. v. London liver pool and Globe Insurance Co.* (1877), 5 Ch.D.569, Per *Jessel M.R.*at 576

¹¹⁷ *Dufourcet v. Bishop* (1886),18 Q.B.D(*Marine Insurance*).

¹¹⁸ *Ellerbeck Collieries, Ltd, v. Cornhill Insurance Ltd.*,[1932] 1 K.B.401 C.A

from the insurers a full indemnity for his loss and retain the salvage, since he would thus be more than fully indemnified.

3.5.6.0. Enforcement of the Right of Subrogation.

The Insurer's right of subrogation as a general rule must be enforced in the name of the Assured¹¹⁹, as subrogation does not entitle the Insurer to enforce such right in his name¹²⁰, except that a right of action is conferred upon him by a Statute¹²¹ or that the assured should make formal assignment¹²² to him of his right of action in respect of the Subject-matter¹²³.

Of serious note it is to understand, that since it is the rights of the insured that passes to the insurer by way of subrogation, the insured is duty bound with reference to the duty to give assistance to the Insurer and the duty not to prejudice the insurer's position.

3.5.6.1 The Insured's duty to give Assistance to the Insurers. The insured must assist, by permitting the Insurers to use his name in any action which he may desire to bring for this purpose¹²⁴ and where the insured refuses the court may compel him to do so upon receiving an indemnity in respect of the costs to be incurred¹²⁵.

3.5.6.2. The Insured's duty not to prejudice the insurer's position. The insured must do no act by which the insurers may be prejudiced.¹²⁶ Therefore, he is not permitted, without the insurers' authority to enforce any claim arising out of the loss himself, and he may upon their application be restrained from doing so¹²⁷. If he is allowed to pursue his case without interference and succeeds, he must account to his Insurers for the amount originally paid under his policy¹²⁸.

3.6.0. THE PRINCIPLE OF ABANDONMENT.

3.6.1. The meaning of abandonment. The Black's Law Dictionary Free Online Legal Dictionary 2nd Ed.

defined abandonment as the voluntary [relinquishment](#) of all rights, title, or claim to property that rightfully belongs to the owner of the property¹²⁹.

The statutory blessing of the principle. The Act provides for this doctrine in the following manner as thus

¹¹⁹ *Dickenson v. Jardine*(1868), L.R. 3 C.P. 639 (marine insurance).

¹²⁰ *London Assurance Co., v. Sainsbury*, (1783), 3 Doug. K.B. 245

¹²¹ Such a right appears to be conferred by S. 4 (1) of the Riot (Damages) Act 1886, Where the Insurers are subrogated to the assured's rights of compensation against the Police authority in the case done by the riot.

¹²² Under the Law of Property Act 1925, S. 136(1)

¹²³ *King v. Victoria Insurance Co.*, (1896) A.C., 250 P.C., where it was an express term of the assignment that the Assured's name was not to be used.

¹²⁴ *Dane v. Mortgage Insurance Corporation* [1894] 1 Q.B.54, C.A.

¹²⁵ *Duus, Brown & Co., v. Bining* (1906), Comm.Cas. (marine insurance)

¹²⁶ *West of England Fire Insurance Co., v. Isaacs* [1897] 1 Q.B. 226 C.A.

¹²⁷ *Law Fire Assurance Co., v. Oakley* (1888), 4 T.L.R. 309

¹²⁸ *Horse, Carriage and General Insurance Co. Ltd., v. Petch* (1916), 33 T.L.R. 13

¹²⁹ <http://thelawdictionary.org/abandonment/>

Subject to any express provision in the policy, there is a constructive total loss where the subject-matter insured is reasonably abandoned on account of its actual total loss appearing to be unavoidable, or because it could not be preserved from actual total loss without an expenditure, which would exceed its value when the expenditure had been incurred¹³⁰.

3.6.2 The Basis for the Principle of Abandonment. The statutory basis for abandonment is constructive total loss. Constructive total loss is described in the Act as follows:

In particular, there is a constructive total loss- where the assured is deprived of the possession of his ship or goods by a peril insured against; and it is unlikely that he can recover the ship or goods as the case may be, or the cost of recovering the ship or goods as the case may be would exceed their value when recovered; or in the case of damage to a ship, where she is so damaged by a peril insured against that the cost of repairing the damage would exceed the value of the ship when repaired; and for the purposes of this paragraph, in estimating the cost of repairs, no deduction is to be made in respect of general average contributions to those repairs payable by other interests, but account is to be taken of the expenses of future salvage operations, and of any future general average contributions to which the ship would be liable if repaired; or in the case of damage to goods, where the cost of repairing the damage and forwarding the goods to their destination would exceed their value on arrival.

3.6.3 Requirement for valid abandonment. Before the insured can claim for constructive total loss, he must abandon the subject matter and give notice of abandonment to the insurers. Thus the Act provides “ Subject to the provisions of this section, where the assured elects to abandon the subject-matter insured to the insurer, he shall give notice of abandonment, and if he fails to give notice of abandonment, the loss shall be treated as a partial loss¹³¹”. This requirement to give notice of abandonment is said to be peculiar to marine insurance as observed by Lord Potter in *Rankin v. Potter*¹³² “In cases of marine insurance the regular mercantile mode of letting the underwriters know that the assured mean to come upon them for a complete indemnity is by giving notice of abandonment, which is a

¹³⁰ S. 61(1)

¹³¹ S.63(1)

¹³² (1873)LR 6HL 83 P.119

very different thing from the abandonment or cession itself”.

3.6.4. Reason for the Notice of abandonment. Lord Justice Cotton, in *The Kaltenbach case* offered two reasons for the requirement of the notice of abandonment as follows. The first is that, on giving the notice the assured “cannot go back from his decision, and the second reason is that, the insurers on the receipt of the notice may then do the best they can and make the most they can as regards the claim and in particular the subject matter insured as what remains of it”.

3.6.5. Forms of notice of abandonment. The Act provides that: “Notice of abandonment may be given in writing, or by word of mouth, or partly in writing and partly by word of mouth, and may be given in terms which indicate the intention of the assured to abandon his insured interest in the subject-matter insured unconditionally to the insurer”¹³³.

3.6.6. Acceptance of notice of abandonment. No duty is imposed on the insurers to accept or reject a notice of abandonment. The Act provides thus:

Where notice of abandonment is properly given, the rights of the assured shall not be prejudiced by the fact that the insurer refuses to accept the abandonment. The acceptance of abandonment may be either express or implied from the conduct of the insurer, but the mere silence of the insurer after notice shall not be construed as an acceptance. Where notice of abandonment is accepted the abandonment is irrevocable, and the acceptance of the notice shall be construed as conclusive admission of liability for the loss and the sufficiency of the notice¹³⁴.

3.6.7. The Implication of a valid abandonment. Where there is a valid abandonment to the insurers, and on acceptance the insurer must pay the total loss and take over the subject matter if they so desired. The Act provides thus:

Where there is a valid abandonment the insurer shall be entitled to take over the interest of the assured in whatever may remain of the subject-matter insured, and all proprietary rights incidental thereto. Upon the abandonment of a ship, the insurer thereof shall be entitled to any freight in course of being earned, and which is earned by her subsequent to the casualty causing the loss, less the expenses of earning it incurred after the casualty; and, where the ship is carrying the owner's goods, the insurer shall be entitled to a reasonable

¹³³ S.63(2)

¹³⁴ S.63(4)-(6)

remuneration for the carriage of them subsequent to the casualty causing the loss¹³⁵.

3.6.8. **When notice of abandonment is not necessary.** There are two clear situations when the notice of abandonment need not to be given the insurers as provided by the Act in section 63(7) and (9). "Notice of abandonment shall be unnecessary where, at the time when the assured receives the information of the loss, there would be no possibility of benefit to the insurer if notice were given to him¹³⁶".

The import of statement that "Notice of abandonment shall be unnecessary where, at the time when the assured receives the information of the loss, there would be no possibility of benefit to the insurer if notice were given to him" was explained in the case of *Vacuum Oil Co., v. Union Insurance Society Canton Ltd.*,¹³⁷. The goods which suffered constructive total loss were cans of petroleum. Some of them were reconditioned and sold by Llyod's agent with the consent of the assured. One of the issues was whether notice of abandonment was necessary. Holding that it is was necessary, the Court of Appeal explained that

"...it is perfectly obvious that the position of things was this, that if the notice of abandonment had been given within a reasonable time, the underwriter had the fullest opportunity of dealing with these goods, they were existence in specie, they were being reconditioned for the purpose of sale for the benefit of whom it might concern, and they were in a condition in which if notice of abandonment had been given within a reasonable time, there was every possibility of benefit to the insurer, because there the goods and he could do what he liked with them."

3.6.9. **Notice of Abandonment and Re-insurance Arrangement.** The Act provides that in a re-insurance contract, the insurer need not to give the re-insurer any notice of abandonment. Thus; "Where an insurer has re-insured his risk, no notice of abandonment need be given by him¹³⁸".

4.0. OBSERVATIONS, RECOMMENDATIONS AND CONCLUSION.

4.1. Observations and recommendations.

The Act neither defined nor described the concept of abandonment. This was a flaw because surrender and forfeiture are synonymous with abandonment but surrender requires agreement while forfeiture can be done against the intention of the party alleged to have forfeited a property. However, the study clearly observed that the abandonment under the marine insurance cannot be

¹³⁵ S.64(1)-(2)

¹³⁶ S.63(7)

¹³⁷ (1926) 25 LIL Rep 546.

¹³⁸ S.63(9)

without the intention to abandon before the external act to abandon. More so the Act failed to take note of this 'intention to abandon' which could have similar import like the general law of contract 'intention to enter legal relations. Likewise, the Act did not offer any definition on proximate cause. Therefore the study recommends that, principle of this kind which thus have vitiating effect in the Act should be defined.

In section 62 of the Act provides that the insured, in the exercise of his right of election can abandon the remains of the subject matter. In respect to this note, the study observed that the law did not state the conduct(s) that can amount to non-abandonment. This pose a very serious concern because where the marine insurance is from warehouse to warehouse and the constructive total loss occurred in the inland waters of receiver of the cargo (which is the subject matter), obviously there is need to keep security of the cargo in specie which may be of benefit to the underwriter. Does it amount to abandonment if the policy holder keeps security of goods in specie which he has abandoned? Or should the policy holder in such circumstances of urgent attention just abandon and let thieves carry the goods in specie and sell them to people who will recondition them? For proper elimination of these question, the study recommends that, this portion of the Act should be reviewed.

In section 63(1), the Act informed the policy holder that, "...if he fails to give notice of abandonment, the loss shall be treated as a partial loss". The question is when will such failure be imputed? It becomes more worrisome when it is read with the section 63(3) caution of 'reasonable diligence' and 'reasonable time' to make inquiry. This unspecific, open ended time frame can be a weapon in the hand of dishonest underwriters who can tell their client to take reasonable time to make enquiry until such insurer will be statute barred to take action against them in respect of indemnification of the constructive loss.

Section 63(7) provides that "Notice of abandonment shall be unnecessary where, at the time when the assured receives the information of the loss, there would be no possibility of benefit to the Insurer if notice were given" This provision seems to be a fantastic trap against the policy holder. My reasons are not far-fetched. First and foremost, the language used is not plain enough and that is why it became one of the main issue in the case of Vacuum Oil Co., v. Union Insurance Society Canton Ltd; until the Court of Appeal have to unveil the meaning. Therefore the study recommends that since the purpose of the Act is to enhance marine insurance contract the language used should be plain enough for an average stakeholders to understand.

Secondly, with the interpretation of the Court of Appeal in the said case, it therefore means that

however minute the value of the remains may be, the notice of abandonment must be given; then what is the essence of this subsection? It is but a trap against the insured! Therefore the study recommends that this provision should be deleted.

Section 63(8) provides: "Notice of abandonment may be waived by the insurer". This standing alone and cannot be read in conjunction with any other subsection before it or after it. It is a 'give-away' to the insurer and it genders several questions. What is the ground of this waiver? Who is the insurer waiving it to? What is the consequence of this waiver on the constructive total loss of the policy holder? With due respect, some Learned authors have read it with subsection 9, which is for notice of abandonment and re-insurance arrangement. Until otherwise proved, there is grammatically no connect between the two. Therefore the provision should be amended.

Unfortunately, section 19 provided for utmost good faith and most unfortunately, the study observed that the doctrine of utmost good faith is no longer relevant in modern marine insurance contracts. The aged doctrine was required those days because the Proposer(the would-be insured) was said to know or presumed to know all that is involved in the transaction as regards risk better than the underwriters, therefore it necessary for the insured to display utmost good faith. With present day technology, underwriters can have all the information they needed without the aid of the proposer.

More so, by the operation of section 54(1) of the Insurance Act, 2003, the insurer is to draw-up a proposal form in such a manner as to contain all such information which the insurer considers to be material. This implies clearly that any information not requested in the proposal form is not material. And since the Insurance Act 2003 is of general application to all insurance businesses, this doctrine of utmost good faith enshrined in the Act is of no effect and the study recommends that it should be removed.

Conclusion

With the accelerated growth of global commercial, maritime activities are also at increase. In fact carriage of goods by sea is very essential to this exponential growth of global commerce. However, there are huge risks attached like: fortuitous accidents, heavy weather, sinking, stranding, collision, including the ordinary actions of the winds and waves. **Fire, war perils, pirates, thieves, barratry, Pollution hazards** among others. Therefore there is the need for a risk management arrangement in helping the growth of global commerce to continue despite these serious risks; hence marine insurance.

From the foregoing, appraising the principles guiding marine insurance is a worthy exercise. There are six principles assessed in this study, three of which are essential to the formation of the

contract of insurance; they are the principle of insurable interest, the principle of indemnity and the principle of utmost good faith (although evaporating); and the other three are observed after the formation of the contract and if not observed can have a vitiating effect on the contract and they are the doctrine of proximate cause, the doctrine of subrogation and the doctrine of abandonment. These last three has to do with claim which is a serious legal issue.

In the light of the above, the study safely concludes that, there should be a review of the extant law to accommodate present-day technology-oriented society of commerce..

References

- Avtar Singh,
Law of Insurance 2nd ed., (Easter Book Company Lucknow 2010)
- Edgar Gold, ALDO Chircop, Hugh kindred
Essentials of Canadian Law – Maritime Law, Marine and Environmental Law
Programme, Dalhousie University (IRWIN LAW)
- Funmi Adeyemi,
Nigerian Insurance Law (2nd edition, Dalson publication Limited, 2007)
- George E. Rejda,
Principles of Risk Management and Insurance 11th edition, Pearson Education 2011
- E. R. Hardy Ivamy,
General Principles of Law, 3rd ed., Butterworth & Co.(Publishers)Ltd. 1975.
- J.O.Irukwu,
Insurance Law and Practice in Nigeria,(revised Ed The caxton Press(West Africa)
Limited Ibadan 1981).
- Olusegun Yerokun,
Insurance Law in Nigeria (Nigeria Revenue Projects Publications 1992.)
- Robert Grime,
Shipping Law,(2nd ed., Sweet & Maxwell 1991)
- Rovert 1 melir and Sandra G. Gustavson
Life Insurances theory and Practices, 4th ed., (Plano,Tx. Business Publications,
1987)

ARTICLE / JOURNALS

A.G. Buabeng , Marine Insurance claims: Understanding the concepts and Tackling the issue: Papers presented at the International Trade and Maritime Conference, 2006 published by Ghana Shippers' Council, 2006; pages 33-94.

Bullentin of the commission on Insurance Technology of the American Risk management and Insurance 11th edition.

Jay S. Bybee, *Profits in Subrogation : An Insurer's Claim to Be More than Indemnified*, 1979 BYU(1979). Available <<http://digitalcommons.law.byu.edu/lawreview/vol1979/iss1/3> pages 145-160

J.C. Sobowale, An Appraisal of the Marine Insurance Act, 1906 and the Recommendation for its Immediate Amendment or Replacement for a New Statute. A paper presented at the 10th Maritime Seminar for Judges, 2009; organized by the Nigerian Shippers' Council in collaboration with the National Judicial Institute, published by Linksoft Nigeria Ltd, Lagos. Pages 218-248.

J.O. Irukwu, Marine Insurance, a paper presented at the Maritime seminar for Judges 6th-8th, December, 1995 Published by the Nigerian Shippers' Council in collaboration with the National Judicial Institute. pages 113-146

Kunle Owoseje, An Overview of Marine Cargo insurance practice in Nigeria; in Shipper Protection in a Developing Economy, Insights Strategies.(vol.2) Network Publishing, a Division of BWO Network Ltd, Ibadan, 2003. copyright by Nigerian Shippers' Council; Editor by Adebayo Sarumi Page 67-107.

INTERNET SOURCES

[http://www.simic.net.cn/news - show.php?id=15025](http://www.simic.net.cn/news-show.php?id=15025) 17/01/2017 10:51pm

<https://www.i.law.com/ilaw/doc/view.htm?id=130514> > accessed 17/01/2017 11:27 pm

<http://www.cila.co.uk/cila/downloads/getting-qualified/certificate/files-2/205-chapter-8-proximate-cause>"

<http://digitalcommons.law.byu.edu/lawreview/vol1979/iss1/3>

<http://www.investopedia.com/terms/s/subrogation.asp> 21/01/2017

<http://www.internationallawoffice.com/Newsletters/Shipping-Transport/Nigeria/Akabogu-Associates/Marine-22/01/2017>

<http://legal-dictionary.thefreedictionary.com/abandonment>, <accessed>

<http://www.dpps-mlas.si/wp-content/uploads/2012/12/Overview-of-Marine-Insurance-Law-Prof.-dr.-Marko-600p.m> 23/01/2017

<https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/premium> 9:28pm 23/01/2017.

<http://thelawdictionary.org/principles/> 11:09pm 23/01/2017

Table of Cases.

Agapitos v, Agnew (The Aegeon) [200] 2 Lloyd's L.R. 42

American Sur. Co. v. Bethlehem Nat'l Bank, 33 F. . Supp. 722,723 (E.D. Pa.).

Amo containers v. Drake Insurance (1984) 51 Nfld& P.E.I.R. 55 (Nfld. S.C. (T.D),

Anchor Marine Insurance v. Keith (1884) 9 S.C.R 483 Clark v. Scottish Imperial Insurance (1897), 4 S.C.R. 192;

Assicuraizoni Generali Tristle v. Express Assurance Corporation Ltd.,[1907]2 K.B. 814 (Marine Insurance).

Balik Furniture and Appliances Ltd v. Maritime Insurance Co. (1978) O.J. No. 1514 (QL); Merchants Marine

Banque Keyser Ullman v. Skandia (1987) 1 Lloyd's Rep. 69 at 9. 93,

Briggs v. merchants traders' ship and insurance Association (1849) 13 QB 167:116 ER 1227

Castellain v. Preston, 11 Q.B.D. 380, 386 (1883):

Catherwood Towing v. Commercial Union Assurance (1996), 26 B.C. LR (3d) 57 (C.A)

Container Transport International Inc. v. Oceanus – underwriters Association (Bermuda) Ltd. (1984) 1 Lloyd's L.R 476;

Crawford v. St. Lawrence Insurance Co (1851) 8 U.C.QB 135 (C.A) Merchants Marine Insurance Co. (1888), 15 S.C.R. 185

CTI v. Oceanus Mutual Underwriting Association (Bermuda) 1984 Lloyd;s Rep 476 at p. 525

Dane v. Mortgage Insurance Corporation [1894] 1 Q.B.54, C.A.

Degreeot v. J.T. O'Bryan and Co. (1979),15 BCLR 271 (C.A)

Descrosiers v. Fishing Vessel Insurance Plan (1994), 87 F.T.R 101

Driscoll v. Millville Marine Insurance Co. (1883), 23 N.B.R. 160 (C.A)

Dudgeon v. Prembroke (1877), 2 App. Cas. 284 (marine insurance)

Dufourcet v. Bishop (1886),18 Q.B.D(Marine Insurance).

Duus, Brown & Co., v. Bining (1906), Comm.Cas. (marine insurance)

Ellerbeck Collieries, Ltd, v. Cornhill Insurance Ltd.,[1932] 1 K.B.401 C.A

Fudge v. Charter Marine Insurance (1992), 97 Nfld. & P.E. I.R. 91 (Nfld. S.C)

General Shipping and forwarding Co. v. British General Insurance Co. (The Borre) (1923) 15 Ll.L.R. 175

Gibson v. Bradford, (1855) 4 E & B 586: 119ER 215

Goole and Hull Steamship Towing Co. v. Ocean Marine Insurance Co (1929), 29LI LR 242

Great Nigeria Insurance Plc v Hepa Global Energy Limited, Suit FHC/L/CS/901/15

Green Forest Lumber v. General Security Insurance, (1980) 1 s.C.r. 176.

Griffiths v. Branley (1878) 4 QBD 70 (CA)

Hicks v. Shield (1857) 7 E & B 633: 119 ER 1380

Horse, Carriage and General Insurance Co. Ltd., v. Petch (1916), 33 T.L.R. 13

Insurance Co. of Canada v. Rumsey (1884), 9 S.C.R. 577; Phoenix Assurance v. Golden Imports (1989), 43 C.C.L.I. 313 (B.C. Co. ct).

Intermunicipality Reality & Development Corp. v. Gore Mutual Insurance Co., (978) 2 F.C. 691

Jumbo United Co. Ltd v. Leadway Assurance Co. Ltd (2016) 15 N.W.L.R. 363-532 at 446.

King v. Victoria Insurance Co.,(1896) A.C., 250 P.C

Law Fire Assurance Co., v. Oakley (1888), 4 T.L.R. 309

Leyland Shipping Co., Ltd. v. Norwich Union Fire Insurance Society, as reported, [1917] 1 K.B. 873 C.A (marine insurance)

London Assurance Co., v. Sainsbury, (1783), 3 Doug. K.B. 245

Lucena V. Craufurd (1806), 2 BOS P.N.R. 269 H.L. (Marine Insurance) p. 302

Manifest shipping & Co v. Uni-Polaris Insurance Co. (The STarsea) (2001) 1 Lloyd's L.R. 389 (HL)

Mansfield v Maitland (1821) 4 B & Ald 582: 106 ER 1049

Mason v. Sainbury (2nd Edn., 1974) pg 481-488

Midland Insurance Co. v. Smith(1881),6 Q.B.D 561

North British and MarcantileInsurance Co. v. London liverpooland Globe Insurance Co. (1877), 5 Ch.D.569, Per Jessel M.R.at 576

North Star Shipping Ltd and Ors v. Sphere Drake Insurance (The North Star) (2006) 691 LMLN2

Orchard v. Aetna Insurance Co. (1856) 5 U.C.C.P 445 (C.A)

Page v. Scottish Insurance Corporation (1929), 140 L.T.571, C.A.

P. Samuel & Co. Ltd v. Damus (1924) All E.R. Rep. 66,H.L.,

Pan Atlantic Insurance Co. v. Pine Top Insurance Co. (1995) AC 501

Pawsey v Scottish Union & National Insurance Company (1908)

Peise v. Aguitar (1811) 3 Taunt 506: 128 ER 201

Peterson Agencies Nigeria Ltd. V. Merary Agencies Company Ltd (1994 F.H.CLR 25

Pink v.Fleming(1890), 25 Q.B.D. 396, C.A.

Rankin v. Potter (1873)LR 6HL 83 P.119

Robertson v. Hamilton, (1811) 14 East 522: 104ER 708

Salomon v. A Salomon & Co., (1897) A.C. 22

Stephen v. Australian Insurance Co. (1872) LR 8 CP 18:43 LJ CP 12

Strive shipping Corp. v. Hellemie Mutual War Risk Association (The Grecia Expression) [2002] 2 Lloyd's L.R. 88

Trew v. Railway Passengers' Assurance Co. (1861),6 H. & N. 839, Ex.Ch.;

Vacuum Oil Co., v. Union Insurance Society Canton Ltd., (1926) 25 LIL Rep 546.

West of England Fire Insurance Co., v. Isaacs [1897] 1 Q.B. 226 C.A.

William France, Fenwick & Co.,Ltd v. Marchants' Marine Insurance Ltd. [1915] 3 K.B. 290, C.A.(marine insurance)

1013799 Ontario Ltd v. Kent Line International (2000). 22 C.C.L.I. (3d) 312 (Omt. S.C)

STATUTES

Insurance Act 2003

Marine Insurance Act cap M2 Law of the Federation Republic of Nigeria 2004

Ghana Insurance Law 1989, PNDCL 277

Under the Law of Property Act 1925, S. 136(1)

S. 4 (1) of the Riot (Damages) Act 1886,

Marine Insurance Act 1906,

Author's name and details: If any.

BEMINI NIMIBOFA PAUL,(LLB., LL.M., BL.)

Lecturer, Faculty of Law, Poma University, Ifangni, Republic of Benin.

Whatsapp 09026914071,

© 2021 by the authors. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

